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House Sales Pricing Prediction King County

HSPPKC

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the House Sales Pricing Prediction King County project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Aleksandra Grishan (e52209173@student.tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	House Sales Pricing King County	Structured text	CSV	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	House Sales Pricing Training Data (70%)	Structured text	CSV	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	House Sales Pricing Test Data (15%)	Structured text	CSV	100 - 1000 MB	no
P4	House Sales Pricing Validation Data (15%)	Structured text	CSV	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "House Sales Pricing King County":

The data in this project is generated by using the King County house sales dataset. The source of the dataset is available on OpenML and is used to develop a predictive model for estimating house prices in King County. The data is analyzed and processed through various techniques such as data cleaning, feature engineering, and model development

using machine learning algorithms in Python. This file, hosted in DBRepo, is permanently accessible (see Chapter 2.2).

Description for "House Sales Pricing Training Data (70%)":

The data contains 70% of the records sampled from the full King County house sales dataset. The data remains uncleaned, unencoded and unscaled, so that these transformers, fitted exclusively on this training subset, can later be applied within the prediction pipeline. This split is used to train the Random Forest Regressor, Gradient Boosting Regressor and XGBoost Regressor models and derive the preprocessing pipeline. The training data is available in DBRepo (see Chapter 2.2).

Description for "House Sales Pricing Test Data (15%)":

The data has a final 15% split reserved for unbiased model evaluation. It maintains the originally uncleaned, unscaled and uncoded format, with encoding and scaling applied only at runtime using transformers derived from the training and validation data. All final performance metrics are reported in the evaluation phase. The test data is published in DBRepo (see Chapter 2.2).

Description for "House Sales Pricing Validation Data (15%)":

The data has a 15% hold-out subset reserved for hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV. Like the training split, it has not yet been encoded, scaled or cleaned. This approach ensures that tuning remains free from data leakage. The validation data is available in DBRepo (see Chapter 2.2).

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	House Sales	https://www.openml.org/search?type=data&status=active&id=42092		no

Description for "House Sales":

This dataset contains house sale prices for King County, which includes Seattle. It includes homes sold between May 2014 and May 2015. It contains 19 house features plus the price and the id columns, along with 21613 observations. It's a great dataset for evaluating simple regression models.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The "House Sales Pricing King County" data in this project is generated by using the King County house sales dataset. The source of the dataset is available on OpenML and is used to develop a predictive model for estimating house prices in King County. The data is analyzed and processed through various techniques such as data cleaning, feature engineering, and model development using machine learning algorithms in Python.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Decision makers in industry

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

I will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames for project files follow the naming convention, which includes a timestamp of creation and version identifiers. This ensures that files can be easily identified, traced, and organized according to their creation time and version. Version control is automated through Git, ensuring that all changes are properly tracked. Each version of the data or document will be associated with a unique identifier (e.g., a timestamp or version number) to avoid any confusion during the project's progress.

As there are no domain-specific metadata standards applicable, I will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used [at file level/at dataset level/at project level]. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, I will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, I will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, I will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

I will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	No	2025-02-28	TU Wien Database Repository	10.82556/hc4f-p120	CC-BY-4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P2	Open	No	2025-02-28	TU Wien Database Repository	10.82556/j118-5e73	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	No	2025-02-28	TU Wien Database Repository	10.82556/bz1k-q291	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	No	2025-02-28	TU Wien Database Repository	10.82556/vdcr-fw15	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it.

<https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To reuse the data, users may need Python and relevant libraries, such as Pandas, NumPy, and Scikit-learn, to analyze and process the dataset. Additionally, users may need tools for data visualization, like Matplotlib or Seaborn, to explore the data effectively.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

I will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

I will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

To provide documentation that will validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse, the following steps will be taken:

- A comprehensive README file will be created for each dataset and script used in the project. This file will include a description of the dataset, its purpose, source, and relevant background information.
- A detailed codebook will be provided to define the variables and explain the structure of the data, ensuring that users can easily understand the dataset. Each dataset will be versioned, with version control used to track changes over time and ensure reproducibility.
- Documentation will specify the versions of software, libraries, and tools used for data processing and analysis to ensure the analysis environment can be replicated.

The dataset will be made freely available, with clear licensing terms that allow for the widest possible reuse. If there are any restrictions on the reuse of the data, these will be explicitly stated, along with any necessary access or use restrictions. This comprehensive

approach to documentation will ensure that the data analysis is validated, reusable, and accessible for future research.

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture, peer review of data.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

ID	File (title + brief description)	Digital type / format	DOI	License	Relation to Data
O1	evaluation_metrics.txt - MAE / MSE / R ² results of the best performing model	Text report / TXT			Documents model performance
O2	rf_best_model.pkl - trained Random Forest model (best GridSearchCV params)	Model artifact / pickle			Trained on P2
O3	gb_best_model.pkl - trained Gradient Boosting model (best GridSearchCV params)	Model artifact / pickle			Trained on P2
O4	xgb_best_model.pkl - trained XGB Boost Regressor model (best GridSearchCV params)	Model artifact / pickle			Trained on P2
O5	learning_rates_vs_r2.png - a figure of R-squared values for different learning rates	Image / PNG			Illustrates tuning process

These five digital artefacts provide a complete view of the modeling workflow in open, widely supported formats. The archive includes three trained model files (Random Forest,

Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost), each saved as a separate pickle file. Additionally, a PNG plot is included that visualizes the results of learning rate tuning for the XGBoost model, showing how model error changed based on learning rate adjustments.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

TU Wien's infrastructure ensures the storage, archiving, and long-term preservation of all project data. The raw merged dataset along with the training, validation, and test splits are stored in DBRepo, while trained models, scalars, and evaluation results are made publicly available via TU Wien Research Data (TUWRD) and assigned individual DOIs. These repositories offer secure data storage, controlled access, and comprehensive metadata management without incurring additional costs.

In this project, Aleksandra Grishan is solely responsible for all aspects of data management. She sourced the original dataset from OpenML, performed the necessary data merging and cleaning, and created the training, validation, and test splits, which are archived in DBRepo. All preprocessing steps, model training (including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost), evaluation, and hyperparameter tuning (such as learning rate optimization) were carried out in a Jupyter notebook environment. The complete workflow—including code, notebooks, and supporting documentation—is available in a public GitHub repository, ensuring full transparency and providing a permanent version history.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

The project's training, validation, and test split files are included in the GitHub repository under the /data directory as a redundant backup. Storing these datasets under version control ensures persistent access and reproducibility, even if the original OpenML dataset becomes unavailable or modified in the future.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

I pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years
P2	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years
P3	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years
P4	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Access to the dataset is controlled by Aleksandra Grishan, who ensures that only authorized individuals or entities are granted access according to the project's needs and compliance requirements. She is responsible for overseeing all aspects of data management, including the control and management of dataset access.

6.3. Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Service Unit of Responsible Research Practices at TU Wien (www.tuwien.at/research-ethics). They are described in detail in separate documents.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?